

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 3, 31 Март

Favorite poet of the Uzbek and Azerbaijani people

Tashkent State Transport University

Obutjonova Durдона Omonjon qizi

Annotation: Shaykhzada not only wrote works in all types and genres of artistic creativity, but also worked effectively as a literary critic and critic.

Key words: works, playwright, critic, literary critic, talent, poems, "Tashkentnoma", buried in Farobi cemetery.

In fact, Maqsud Shaykhzoda, who was a blood-blooded Azerbaijani, and later became famous as a truly beloved poet, writer, dramatist, and outstanding scientist of the Uzbek people, was born in 1908 in the city of Oktash, Ganja region of Azerbaijan. His father, Ma'sumbek, was a doctor with a great reputation in the country.

In his poetry, Shaykhzada wrote his pen mainly on modern themes, and in his dramaturgy, he took a deep look at the historical past and gave a new artistic life to figures and events that help to illuminate modern problems in it. In the last years of his life, he wrote the last play about Beruni.

Sheikhzade not only wrote works in all types and genres of artistic creation, but also worked effectively as a literary critic and critic. Sheikhzada, who published the monograph "Genius Poet" as early as 1941, was constantly engaged in Navoi's life and work until the last days of his life.

After the article "About Navoi's Lyrical Hero" (1948), which he wrote on the occasion of Navoi's 500th anniversary, "About some poetic methods of Navoi's lyrics" (1959), "In the Art Studio of the Master" (3-part article, 1965-66), "Sultan of Ghazal property" (1966), "From the History of Tazkirachilik" (1968), created major scientific researches and brought the science of narcotics to a new stage of development.

Representatives of the Uzbek folklore such as Fazil Shair, works such as "Alpomish", "Shirin bilan Shakar", Uzbek classic and modern literature Babur, Muqimi, Furqat, Oybek, Gafur Ghulam, Hamid Olimjon, world literature Nizami Ganjavi, Sh. Rustaveli, A.S. Pushkin, N.A. Nekrasov, A.N. Ostrovsky, T.G. Shevchenko, A.P. He wrote works dedicated to his figures, such as Chekhov. As a pedagogue, scientist and poet, he made a worthy contribution to the development of a generation of poets, literary critics and critics.

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 3, 31 Март

In 1929, the first poem of the young poet in Uzbek language was published in the pages of the newspaper "Sharq Haqiqat". Shortly after that, Shaykhzoda's first collection "Ten Poems", later "Undoshashim" (1933), "The Third Book" (1934), and "Jumhuriyat" (1935) were published.

Maqsud Sheikhzada said that "the labor heroism of our people, struggle and battle, freedom and friendship, happiness and sorrow, the beautiful landscapes of the country and the spiritual beauty of man became familiar to my pen and meaningful to my tongue."

These qualities of the poet were first of all manifested in his new, unique images capable of expressing changes and situations in life, reality and the spiritual world of our people. These are the images of History - Road - Journey - Ship - Caravan, Map (Earth and Homeland), Address, Number, Speed and Time. These are inextricably linked with each other, the history of mankind is integral and always moves forward, this human caravan - the ship cannot be stopped, it moves towards the destination of the human dream - happiness.

This can be seen from the fact that Sheikhzadeh titles his books as "Fifteen-year notebook" or "Quarter-century book". The poet himself says that "Human life is a notebook with a limited deadline", which means that this notebook should be filled with useful and noble deeds - "writings". The poem "Numbers" contains the following lines: "I am neither an astrologer nor an accountant, but I see heavenly meanings in the core of numbers, which make the country beautiful"...

In the poem "Hands", he sees in hands the existence of a person, the seal of his inner world. According to him, there are "very compassionate, life-giving hands" and "cruel, evil, cold as a grave, lazy" hands, in short, each hand is "the handmaiden of the heart", whatever the heart commands, it does. This is what he does.

One of the works that testify to the creative maturity of Maqsud Sheikhzadeh is the epic "Tashkentnoma". Literary community at the time evaluated this epic as a major creative success of the poet in our literature. Indeed, "Tashkentnoma" is the most complete of Sheikhzoda's epics, in which the unique aspects of the poet's personality are clearly revealed. The uniqueness of the epic is that the work is not built on the basis of a single story.

Sheikhzada was a multifaceted talent. Along with poems and epics, he also created dramas of very high artistic power. Not counting the drama "Beruni",

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 3, 31 Март

which Sheikhzade started writing at the end of his life, but did not finish, his dramas "Jalaluddin Manguberdi" and "Mirzo Ulugbek" have already become the artistic property of our people.

Sheikhzadeh's works have been translated into sister nations and foreign languages. In the process of translation, the poet received education from the master school of the representatives of brotherly nations and representatives of world literature, and wrote poems embodying the advanced traditions.

Sheikhzadeh died on February 19, 1967. He was buried in the Farobi cemetery of Tashkent.

References:

1. Mamurova, F. I. (2023). The Fundamental Theorem of Axonometry and Axonometric Projections. AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND LEARNING FOR DEVELOPMENT, 2(4), 223-226.
2. Islamovna, M. F. (2024). THE CREATION OF MAQSUD SHAYKHZODA-AS A GOLDEN LEGACY. " XXI ASRDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi, 2(1), 90-93.
3. Mamurova, F., & Obutjonova, D. (2023). KKI XALQ DILBANDI-MAQSUD SHAYXZODA. Бюллетень студентов нового Узбекистана, 1(11), 12-13.
4. Mamurova, F. I. (2023, November). KKI XALQ DILBANDI-MAQSUD SHAYXZODA. In International conference on multidisciplinary science (Vol. 1, No. 5, pp. 51-52).
5. Farxodovich, P. G. U. (2023, May). Elastik Poydevor Ustidagi Nurlarni Hisoblash Uchun. In International Conference on Multidimensional Research and Innovative Technological Analyses (pp. 198-202).
6. Ilhom o'g'li, M. E., & Oybek o'g'li, K. A. (2023, November). MAQSUD SHAYXZODA HAYOTI VA IJODINI TARG 'IB QILISH. In International conference on multidisciplinary science (Vol. 1, No. 5, pp. 53-55).
7. Mamurova, F. I., & Mustafoev, E. (2021, October). Aksonometrik Proyeksiyalarning Asosiy Teoremasi. Dimmetrik Aksonometriya Qurish. In " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 100-103).

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 3, 31 Март

8. Mamurova, F. I. ugli Mustafayev, EI (2021). SHADOWS IN A PERSPECTIVE BUILDING. Conferencious Online, 16-18.

9. Amirkulovich, T. S. (2023, May). APPLICATION OF MODERN SMALL MECHANISMS IN RAILWAY TRACK REPAIR. In Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes (pp. 172-176).

10. Mikhailovna, M. M., Uglu, M. E. I., & Uglu, K. J. J. (2023). DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES WHEN PERFORMING WEIGHING CALCULATIONS. Horizon: Journal of Humanity and Artificial Intelligence, 2(6), 44-46.

11. Sulaymanovna, S. S. (2023, May). «CHANGING EDUCATIONAL STRATEGIES FOR TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AT UNIVERSITY: FROM LEARNING TO TEACHING STRATEGIES. In Proceedings of International Conference on Educational Discoveries and Humanities (Vol. 2, No. 6, pp. 103-108).

12. Pirnazarov, G. U. F. (2023). KO ‘NDALANG KESIMI TRAPETSIYASIMON BO ‘LGAN TEMIR BETON TUTASH BALKALARNI HARAKATLANUVCHI YUKKA HISOBLASH. SO ‘NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI, 6(5), 29-34.

13. Mamurova, F. I., & Mustafoev, E. (2021). Basic Theorem of Axonometric Projections. Dimetric Axonometry Construction. In ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 100-103).

14. Tursunnazar o‘g‘li, O. J., & Ilhom o‘g‘li, M. E. (2023, May). ODDIY FERMA STERJENLARIDA QO‘ZG‘ALMAS YUKLAR TA‘SIRIDAN ZO‘RIQISHLARNI TOPISH, ODDIY FERMA STERJENLARIDAGI ZO‘RIQISHLARI UCHUN TA‘SIR CHIZIQLAR QURISH VA ULARNI BERILGAN YUK BILAN YUKLASH. In International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics (pp. 262-268).

15. Begali o‘g‘li, A. E., Ilhom o‘g‘li, M. E., & Tursunnazar o‘g‘li, O. J. (2023). EKS KAVATORLAR BILAN GRUNT QAZISH TEXNOLOGIYALARI. MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH, 2(24), 132-140.

**МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ:
ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА**

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

SJIF 2024 = 5.444

Том 2, Выпуск 3, 31 Март

16. Xalilova, R. X., & Ilhom o'g'li, V. E. (2022, December). ATMOSFERANI MUHOFAZA QILISH. In " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 120-123).
17. Ilhom o'g'li, M. E. (2022). KO 'P PROLYOTLI SHARNERLI BALKALARNI XARAKATLANUVCHI YUK TA'SIRIGA HISOBLASH. In " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 250-254).
18. Shohjaxon Maxamadro'zi o'g, U., & Ilhom o'g'li, M. E. (2022). TEMIR YO 'L TRANSPORTIDA BINO VA INSHOOTLAR QURILISHI. In " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 234-237).
19. Begali o'g'li, A. E., & Ilhom o'g'li, M. E. (2022). TEMIR YO 'LLAR QURILISHIDA BETON VA TEMIRBETON VAZIFALARI. In " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 246-249).
20. Mamurova, F. I., & ugli Mustafayev, E. I. (2021). SHADOWS IN A PERSPECTIVE BUILDING. Conferencious Online, 16-18.